

MODERN MEANS OF INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF EDUCATION

Salieva Olima Kamalovna

Candidate of technical sciences, associate professor
Bukhara Engineering-Technological Institute
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Abstract. In his activities, the teacher must solve not only educational problems, but also create conditions for students to develop creative search, encourage them to research activities, and form orientation skills in a vast information space. And as a necessary condition in solving the tasks set, the introduction of information technologies into all components of the educational process is considered. A constantly evolving information system, combined with technical support, ensures a solid process.

Key words: teaching, educational system, research activities, a speech, report, defense of a project.

Introduction. One of the current and widespread areas for the introduction of information technologies in the educational process is multimedia presentation technologies. Now lectures in the form of presentations are used by teachers of almost all subjects.

Now a presentation is not only a speech, report, defense of a project, etc., but also electronic documents of a special kind, characterized by complex multimedia content and special playback control capabilities.

In other words, a presentation is another way for a lecturer to communicate with an audience. This is communication on a different level, which makes it possible to improve the process of presenting and understanding the material by the audience.

Electronic presentations, unlike electronic textbooks, are intended, as a rule, to solve local pedagogical problems. The use of electronic presentations can significantly increase the information content, efficiency and dynamism of the lecture. Obviously, in this case, the quality of the learning process is significantly increased, since in this situation both visual, auditory, and visual channels of perception are simultaneously involved (modality principle).

The method of conducting lectures using electronic presentations can be different. The purpose of the presentation may be to study new material and / or consolidate it, as well as to compare it with previously studied material.

It makes sense to put on the slides not the text of the lecture, but only its “basic abstract”, the undeniable advantages of which are:

- compact presentation of information;
- the presence of elements of generalization and systematization of knowledge on the studied discipline (sections, topics);
- reliance in the text on the essence of concepts, omitting their definitions, otherwise the mechanism for comprehending the text is lost when writing it.

A special place is given to the problem of forming the structure of the presentation - the presence and composition of the mandatory structural elements: cover, title slide, table of contents, educational material and brief conclusions on the topic.

On the other hand, it is almost indisputable that the presentation design has the most direct and effective impact on the motivation of trainees, the speed and depth of perception of the material, and a number of other important indicators. Therefore, the design of the interface of the learning environment should not be developed on an intuitive level, a reasonable and balanced system approach is required. When creating a multimedia lecture, the following should be taken into account:

- the information on the screen must be clearly structured;
- visual information should be periodically interrupted by audio information (ie viewing the text of the lecture should be accompanied by the teacher's comments);
- Color brightness and/or sound volume should vary periodically.

When using "color" in their presentations, it must be remembered that students most often watch presentations not on a computer, but on a projector, which imposes its own characteristics on color reproduction.

When creating electronic presentations, it is recommended to arrange objects:

- close to each other, since the closer the objects in the visual field are to each other, the more likely they will be transformed into single, integral images;
- taking into account the peculiarities of highlighting an object and background when choosing the shape of objects, sizes of letters and numbers, color saturation, text arrangement, etc.;
- without overloading visual information with details, bright and contrasting colors, moving objects (although exceptions are possible to create special effects);
- highlighting educational material intended for memorization with color, underlining, font type and size, etc.

Color transitions on the background of the slide, moving, unfinished objects attract attention and are quickly remembered, respectively, after viewing slides with such a design, it is the design, and not the text on the slide, that remains in memory.

In addition, when creating presentations, it must be taken into account that objects depicted in different colors and on different backgrounds are perceived differently by a person. If the brightness of the color of objects and the brightness of the background differ significantly from the relative "visibility" curve, then a superficial examination of the image may cause the effect of a "psychological spot", when some objects seem to fall out of the field of view or their consideration requires additional visual effort. An important role in the organization of visual information is played by the contrast of objects in relation to the background.

The ratio of colors in the color palette of an electronic learning tool can also form a certain psychological mood. One of The main components of the design of a pedagogical presentation is to take into account the physiological characteristics of the perception of color and shape. For example, the predominance of dark colors can lead to the development of a depressed psychological state, passivity, while the predominance of bright colors, on the contrary, can lead to overexcitation, and the general overexcitation of the body often borders on the rapid development of fatigue of the visual analyzer.

For the convenience of working with the presentation, it makes sense to add headers and footers to the presentation (indicating the topic of the lecture, section, teacher's name, page numbers) and controls: buttons for moving from the table of contents to the beginning of topics; buttons for moving from slide to slide forward and backward; button to return to the table of contents; end button, etc.

Taking into account all these features of the design of the presentation to a large extent affects the effectiveness of the perception of the information presented in it.

The main factors indicating the intensification of the educational process with the help of electronic presentations can be:

- increasing the purposefulness of training;
- increasing the effectiveness of training (in the same time it is possible to present more material with the same or with a higher coefficient of assimilation);
- strengthening motivation and increasing interest in the subject;
- improvement of students' emotional state.

The technical equipment of our institute includes several multimedia computer classes, auditoriums equipped with projectors. In combination with the available information electronic resources, it creates the basis for a successful solution educational task..

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